

Romieg Soca

Description of ten new *Ophrys*-hybrids (*Orchidaceae*) of the Abruzzo (Italy)

Keywords

Orchidaceae, *Ophrys brutia*, *Ophrys dinarica*, *Ophrys incubacea*, *Ophrys lucana*, *Ophrys passionis* subsp. *majellensis*, *Ophrys pinguis*, *Ophrys romolinii*, *Ophrys tetraloniae*, *Ophrys* × *brunamontei*, *Ophrys* × *capistrelloi*, *Ophrys* × *catinii*, *Ophrys* × *impresciae*, *Ophrys* × *lociceroides*, *Ophrys* × *palenae*, *Ophrys* × *pescocanalei*, *Ophrys* × *piconei*, *Ophrys* × *recchiai*, *Ophrys* × *vernacchiai*, hybrids, Flora of Abruzzo, Italy.

Summary

Soca, R. (2014): Description of ten new *Ophrys*-hybrids (*Orchidaceae*) of the Abruzzo (Italy).- J. Eur. Orch. 46 (3/4): 661-678.

Identification, description and sites of ten new hybrids of the genus *Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) from the Abruzzo region (Italy). The Abruzzo region, which is rather seldom visited by botanists, offers a wide range of biotopes and microclimates. An insight into the botanical wealth was provided in the recent work by ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012) and is supplemented by this paper. The Abruzzo region should become a popular destination for the botanists and orchid experts, since many taxa are still to be studied.

Zusammenfassung

Soca, R. (2014): Beschreibung von zehn neuen *Ophrys*-Hybriden (*Orchidaceae*) der Abruzzen (Italien).- J. Eur. Orch. 46 (3/4): 661-678.

Zehn bisher unbekannte Hybriden der Gattung *Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) aus den Abruzzen (Italien) werden beschrieben und ihre Fundorte sowie Verbreitung mitgeteilt. Diese Region, die eher selten von Botanikern besucht wird, besitzt ein breites Spektrum von Biotopen und Mikroklimata. In der vorliegenden Arbeit werden die Hinweise auf ihren botanischen Reichtum in ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012) ergänzt. Die Abruzzen bieten ein attraktives Ziel für Botaniker und Orchideen-Experten für weitere Untersuchungen unzureichend bekannter Sippen.

Riassunto

Soca, R. (2014): Descrizione di dieci nuovi ibridi d'*Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) di Abruzzo (Italia).- J. Eur. Orch. 46 (3/4): 661-678.

Viene comunicata l'identificazione, descrizione e localizzazione, di dieci nuovi ibridi del genere *Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) della regione Abruzzo (Italia). Questa regione, poco percorsa dai botanici, offre una grande diversità di biotopi e microclimi. Un esempio della ricchezza botanica è stato presentato nel recente lavoro di ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012), questo articolo ne è un supplemento. L'Abruzzo dovrebbe venire una destinazione di scelta per i botanici ed orchidofili poiché restano ancora da studiare numerosi taxa.

Résumé

Soca, R. (2014): Description de dix nouveaux hybrides d'*Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) des Abruzzes (Italie).- J. Eur. Orch. 46 (3/4): 661-678.

Localisation, identification et description de dix nouveaux hybrides d'*Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) de la région des Abruzzes (Italie). Cette région, peu parcourue par les botanistes, offre une grande diversité de biotopes et microclimats. Un aperçu de la richesse botanique a été initié dans le récent ouvrage de ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012), cet article en est un complément. La région des Abruzzes devrait être une destination de choix pour les botanistes et orchidophiles car de nombreux taxons restent à étudier.

* * *

1. Introduction

During the last few years, the author has found several hundred hybrids of *Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*), among which approximately slightly over one hundred undescribed ones. Most of them grow in Italy, a country where the author has spent many months in the last few years, quite often in the Abruzzo region. A description of ten new *Ophrys* hybrids from this region is given below.

The Abruzzo region, situated in the center of Italy, covers 10.794 km², accounting for about 4 % of the surface of Italy. As regards natural areas, it is characterized by the fact that over one third of its surface is classified as a national or regional natural park or nature reserve; the Abruzzo national park is one of the oldest parks in Europe. This park has suffered many setbacks since it was gazetted in 1922; 2013 was a year marked by murders of bears and wolves. Severe damages are caused to the indigenous flora by wild boars and introduced deers. A difference in elevation of nearly three thousand meters

from the Adriatic Sea to the Gran Sasso involves a wide range of biotopes and microclimates.

Fig 1: Fresco, dating 1263, on the vault of the Oratory of San Pellegrino (Bominaco, Caporciano, L'Aquila).

As regards arts, the oldest known fresco where an *Ophrys* is displayed belongs to Abruzzo. This fresco was painted in 1263 and *Ophrys* plants can be seen on the front wall at the foot of saint Onuphrius as well as on the vault of the San Pellegrino oratory (Bominaco, Caporciano, L'Aquila) (fig.1).

The author has been particularly impressed and delighted by the Abruzzo region, which he has discovered with botanists from Roma and other local friends; this paper was written to thank and pay tribute to them.

The author discloses just a few of these many hybrids, which are easy interpretable and whose individual features are clearly intermediate between those of both parents. The coordinate system used in this paper is UTM_{WGS84}.

2. History of the studies on the *Ophrys* genus of the area of the Abruzzo

Since Michele Tenore in the early 19th century, the genus *Ophrys* has received little attention from a floristic point of view in the Abruzzo region. The following is a rather short list of literature references that can be referred to for a better knowledge of the Abruzzo flora: CENTURIONE (1999), COLELLA et al. (2011), CONTI (1990, 1995, 1998), CONTI et al. (2006), CONTI & MANZI (2012), CONTI & PELLEGRINI (1990), CONTI & TINTI (2008), DAISS & DAISS (1996), DI CECCO & PEZZETTA (2012), DI PEDE (2001), DI SANTO & PEZZETTA (2012), GALETTI (1995), GRIEBL (2010), HERTEL & PRESSER (2006, 2009), LASTORIA (1988), PARIS & SCIVOLA (2011), ROMOLINI & SOCA (2011a, 2011b), SOUCHE (2008a, 2008b), TAMMARO (1986), TINTI & CONTI (2002).

3. New *Ophrys*-hybrids from Abruzzo

3.1 *Ophrys* × *palenae* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. brutia P.Delforge × *O. passionis* Sennen subsp. *majellensis* (Helga Daiss & Herm. Daiss) Romolini & Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip similar to *Ophrys passionis* subsp. *majellensis*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys brutia*.

Description: plant 39 cm tall; 5 basal leaves; 4 flowers; sepals oblong, elongate, light green; petals oblong, green with wavy edges tinged with orange, two-thirds of the sepal length; lip entire, convex, round, blackish brown with a merely basal hairy margin; speculum with simple, weakly differentiated markings; apical appendage minute within a deep indentation; stigmatic cavity and basal area brown tinged with orange; pseudo-eyes green; column connective at right angle to the lip; pollinia yellow; flowers in May.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Palena, San Cataldo, alt. 900 m. 33T 04270 46464.

Holotypus: 26.5.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub

n°RS.2011.526.

Etymology: after the name of the city “Palena”, the place where the hybrid was found first.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 2; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 514.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (CH).

3.2 *Ophrys* × *vernacchiae* Soca, **hybr. nat. nov.**

O. brutia P.Delforge × *O. romolinii* Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip similar to *Ophrys romolinii*, and the stigmatic cavity, sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys brutia*.

Description : plant 32 cm tall; 7 basal leaves; 5 flowers; sepals oblong, green suffused with red; petals oblong reddish; lip entire elongate, with strongly recurved edges, a very hairy margin, blackish, slightly developed bulges; speculum comprising two elongate lines, bluish; apical appendage large, green, yellowish; stigmatic cavity and basal area blackish; pseudo-eyes blackish; column connective obtuse; pollinia yellow; flowers in May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Gamberale, Colle Vernacchia,. alt. 1177 m. 33T 04347 46383.

Holotypus: 6.6.2010. Coll. Romieg Soca, cons. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2010.606.

Etymology: named after “Colle Vernacchia”, the place where the hybrid was found first.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 4a, 4b; SOUCHE 2008: 198.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Calabria (CS), Campania (CE), Abruzzo (AQ), (CH), (PE), Puglia (TA).

Specimina selecta: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Gamberale, Colle Vernacchia,. alt. 1222 m, 33T 04346 46386, 26.5.2011, leg. Romieg Soca RS.2011.519 (MPU); Calabria, Cosenza, Saracena, 1600 m au sud de Zoccalia, alt, 216 m, 33S 06009 44000, 26.4.2005, leg. Romieg Soca RS.2005.463 (MPU).

Remarks : I have spotted many such hybrids in four regions and six provinces at elevations ranging from 200 to 1400 m. Delforge first reported it in the paper where he described *O. brutia* (DELFORGE 2003: 82, 88).

Personal field records: Italia, Abruzzo (AQ), Aielli, 700 m east of the village, Cerano, alt. 1055 m, 33T 03846 46598, 11.6.2010; Rivisondoli, Colle Pugnarese, alt. 1340 m, 33T 04263 46323, 26.5.2011; Abruzzo (CH), Gamberale, San Lorenzo, alt. 1222 m, 33T 04346 46386, 26.5.2011; Palena,

San Cataldo, alt. 900 m, 33T 04270 46464, 26.5.2011; Abruzzo (PE), Popoli, Spallone, alt. 419 m, 33T 04029 46712, 5.5.2012; Calabria (CS), Saracena, 1600 m South of Zoccalia, alt. 216 m, 33S 06009 44000, 26.4.2005; 28.4.2006; 2.5.2006; Campania (CE), Gallo Matese, Valle Delizia, alt. 838 m, 33T 04350 45924, 12.5.2013; Gallo Matese, Monte Cenamilli, alt. 850 m, 33T 04329 45913, 8.5.2013; Puglia (TA), Martina Franca, Buffaloria (Monte Trazzonara), alt. 404 m, 33T 07016 45000, 28.4.2009.

3.3 *Ophrys* × *recchia* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *O. incubacea* Bianca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip similar to *Ophrys dinarica*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys incubacea*.

Description : plant 25 cm tall; 5 basal leaves; 5 flowers; sepals oblong elongate, light green; petals triangular, elongate, erect, reddish brown; lip entire, sharply convex, elongate, blackish brown, with a very hairy margin; speculum with an intricate pattern, comprising two branched elongate lines, reddish, surrounded by a greenish yellow line; basal area blackish brown; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes olive green; column connective obtuse; pollinia yellow; flowers in May.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Collepietro, Monte Ospedalera, alt. 651 m, 33T 04010 46717.

Holotypus: 20.5.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2011.515.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Giuseppe Recchia, a naturalist from Luco dei Marsi, Italia, Abruzzo (AQ).

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 3; SOUCHE 2008: 87, ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 535.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ, PE).

Specimina selecta: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Collepietro, Monte Ospedalera, 10.5.2007, coll. Rolando Romolini, leg. in herb. FI sub n° Romolini SN.

Personal field records: Italia, Abruzzo (AQ), Collepietro, Monte Ospedalera, alt. 652 m, 33T 04009 46717, 10.5.2007; 20.5.2011; Pacentro, Pian dell'Orso, alt. 1049 m, 33T 04190 46561, 9.6.2010; Aielli, Cerano, alt. 1055 m, 33T 03846 46598, 11.6.2010; Aielli, Croce, alt. 1036 m, 33T 03826 46604, 21.5.2011; Aielli, Reniccia, alt. 1044 m, 33T 03826 46605, 19.5.2012; Aielli, Strepata, alt. 1045 m, 33T 03846 46598, 24.5.2011; Aielli, Strepata, alt. 1047 m, 33T 03846 46598, 19.5.2012; Abruzzo (PE), Popoli, Spallone, alt. 419 m,

33T 04029 46712, 5.5.2012.

Abruzzo (AQ). Pacentro. Pian dell'Orso. 9.6.2012. R. Romolini com. pers.; Petrucci, 2013: 97.

3.4 *Ophrys ×brunamontei* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *O. passionis* Sennen subsp. *majellensis* (Helga Daiss & Herm.Daiss) Romolini & Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip similar to *Ophrys dinarica*, and the stigmatic cavity, pseudo-eyes, sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys passionis* subsp. *majellensis*.

Description : plant 27 cm tall; 5 basal leaves; 4 flowers; sepals oblong elongate, pinkish white; petals yellowish with orange-tinged edges; lip entire, convex, round, blackish brown, with a fairly hairy margin; speculum pattern comprising two branched elongate lines; apical appendage small, triangular, basal area orange green; stigmatic cavity light green; pseudo-eyes green; column connective obtuse; pollinia yellow; flowers in late May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Palena, San Cataldo, alt. 900 m, 33T 04270 46464.

Holotypus: 26.5.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2011.523.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Francesca Romana Brunamonte, a naturalist from Roma, Italia.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 5; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 535.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (CH).

3.5 *Ophrys ×impresciae* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *O. pinguis* Romolini & Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip and stigmatic cavity similar to *Ophrys pinguis*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys dinarica*.

Description : plant 35 cm tall; 7 basal leaves; 10 flowers; sepals oblong elongate, reddish pink; petals triangular elongate, red; lip entire quadrangular convex, blackish brown, with short hairs, bulges weakly developed; speculum brown and purple blue surrounded by a broad yellowish white line; apical appendage yellowish green, tridentate, forwardly directed, inserted within a very deep indentation; basal area blackish brown; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes blackish green; column connective slightly obtuse; pollinia

yellow, flowers in May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Capistrello, Selvetta, alt. 721 m, 33T 03661 46454.

Holotypus: 8.6.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2011.630.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Ugo Imprescia, a naturalist from Roma.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 6; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 535.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ).

Personal field records: Italia, Abruzzo (AQ), Ateleta, Solagna, alt. 829 m, 7.6.2010, 33T 04342 46341.

3.6 *Ophrys ×piconei* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *O. romolinii* Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip and petals similar to *Ophrys romolinii*, and the speculum and stigmatic cavity similar to *Ophrys dinarica*.

Description : plant 28 cm tall; 6 basal leaves; 4 flowers; sepals oblong, pink; petals elongate with parallel, ciliate edges, pink; lip entire rectangular, with strongly recurved edges and a very hairy margin, blackish brown, bulges weakly developed; speculum large, intricate, covering three quarters of the lip, surrounded by a greyish line; apical appendage large, forwardly directed, yellowing green; basal area orange brown, stigmatic cavity blackish brown; pseudo-eyes blackish brown; column connective at right angle to the lip; pollinia yellow; flowers in late May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Palena, Girone, alt. 906 m, 33T 04273 46461.

Holotypus: 6.6.2010. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2010.604.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Giampaolo Picone, a naturalist from Roma.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 7a, 7b; SOUCHE 2008: 189, ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 535.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ, CH).

Personal field records: Italia, Abruzzo (AQ), Aielli, Croce, alt. 1036 m, 33T 03826 46604, 21.5.2011; Aielli, Reniccia, alt. 1044 m, 33T 03826 46605, 19.5.2012; Aielli, Strepata, alt. 1045 m, 33T 03846 46598, 24.5.2011; Aielli, Strepata, alt. 1047 m, 33T 03846 46598, 19.5.2012; Lecce nei Marsi, Madonna

Delle Grazie, alt. 938 m, 33T 03895 46421, 29.5.2012; Abruzzo (CH), Palena, San Cataldo, alt. 900 m, 33T 04270 46464, 14.5.2007; 26.5.2011; Abruzzo (CH), Palena, Girone, 26.5.2011.

Abruzzo (CH). Palena. Girone. alt. 906 m. 33T 04273 46461. 11.6.2012. R. Romolini com. pers.; Petrucci, 2013: 99.

3.7 *Ophrys* × *capistrelloi* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. dinarica Kranjčev & P.Delforge × *O. tetraloniae* W.P.Teschner

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip, stigmatic cavity and apical appendage similar to *Ophrys tetraloniae*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys dinarica*.

Description : plant 37 cm tall; 7 basal leaves; 11 flowers; sepals oblong elongate, reddish pink; petals nearly triangular, red; lip entire quadrangular, round, convex, blackish brown, with short hairs, bulges strongly developed; speculum large, intricate, covering the basal half of the lip, reddish brown, surrounded by a broad yellowish white line; apical appendage large and broad, forwardly directed, yellowish green; basal area dark brown; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes dark green; column connective short; pollinia yellow; flowers in late May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Capistrello, Selvetta, alt. 754 m, 33T 03661 46454.

Holotypus: 8.6.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2011.601.

Etymology: after the name of the city (Capistrello) where it was first recorded.

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 8.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ).

Specimina selecta: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Capistrello, Selvetta, 600 m au sud-ouest de Pescocanale, 33T 03661 46454, 8.6.2011, coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU sub n° RS.2011.631.

3.8 *Ophrys* × *lociceroi* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. lucana P.Delforge, Devillers-Tersch. & Devillers × *O. passionis* Sennen subsp. *majellensis* (Helga Daiss & Herm.Daiss) Romolini & Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip and stigmatic cavity similar to *Ophrys lucana*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys passionis* subsp. *majellensis*.

Description : plant 19 cm tall; 5 basal leaves; 6 flowers; sepals oblong, green, dorsal sepal with a helmet-like wrapped edge; petals elongate with parallel edges, yellowish green; lip entire convex with reflexed edges, more hairy on along the edges, dark reddish brown; speculum small, rough X-shaped; apical appendage small, triangular, reddish; basal area reddish brown; stigmatic cavity V-ended, yellowish green; column connective short; pollinia yellow; flowers in late May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Chieti, Palena, San Cataldo, alt. 932 m, 33T 04270 46466.

Holotypus: 6.6.2010. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2010.603.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Alessio Locicero, a naturalist from Vallepietra (RM).

Ecology: dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 9; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 536.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (CH).

3.9 *Ophrys ×catinii* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. pinguis Romolini & Soca × *O. romolinii* Soca

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip and stigmatic cavity similar to *Ophrys romolinii*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys pinguis*.

Description : plant 20 cm tall; 5 basal leaves; 6 flowers; sepals oblong elongate, reddish pink, the dorsal sepal narrower and bent backwards; petals elongate, nearly triangular, reddish pink with darker edges; lip entire quadrangular, round, convex, blackish brown, with a very hairy margin; speculum large and simple, brownish red surrounded by a whitish line; apical appendage yellowish green, triangular, forwardly directed, inserted within a very deep indentation; basal area blackish brown; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes blackish green; column connective obtuse and short; pollinia yellow; flowers in late May-June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Capistrello, Selvetta, alt. 761 m, 33T 03662 46454.

Holotypus: 20.5.2013, Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2013.502.

Etymology: named as a tribute to Vincenzo Catini, a naturalist from Rosciolo dei Marsi, Italia, Abruzzo (AQ).

Ecology: dry grasslands and rocky fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 10; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 537.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ).

Personal field records: Italia, Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, Selvetta, 600 m South-west of Pescocanale, alt. 761 m, 33T 03662 46454, 28.5.2012.

3.10 *Ophrys* ×*pescocanalei* Soca, hybr. nat. nov.

O. pinguis Romolini & Soca × *O. tetraloniae* W.P.Teschner

Diagnosis: The new hybrid is characterized for the lip and stigmatic cavity similar to *Ophrys tetraloniae*, and the sepals and petals similar to *Ophrys pinguis*.

Description : plant 30 cm tall; 6 basal leaves; 12 flowers; sepals reddish, lateral sepals oblong nearly triangular, dorsal sepal with parallel edges; petals triangular, reddish pink, becoming darker from the center to the edges; lip entire quadrangular convex, blackish brown, with short hairs, bulges weakly developed; speculum small and simple, located at the base of the lip, purplish brown; apical appendage large and broad, forwardly directed, yellowish green; basal area dark brown; stigmatic cavity blackish; pseudo-eyes blackish green; column connective obtuse and short; pollinia yellow; flowers in June.

Terra typica: Italia, Abruzzo, Aquila, Capistrello, Selvetta, alt. 721 m, 33T 03661 46454.

Holotypus: 8.6.2011. Coll. Romieg Soca, leg. in herb. MPU. sub n°RS.2011.632.

Etymology: after the name of the village (Pescocanale) where it was first recorded.

Ecology : dry grasslands and fallow fields on calcareous substrates.

Iconography: in hoc op.: fig. 11; ROMOLINI & SOUCHE 2012: 283.

Distribution in Italy (pers. obs.): Abruzzo (AQ).

4. Conclusion

Lots of taxa are still to be studied in the Abruzzo region, which is seldom visited by botanists. In the last work of ROMOLINI & SOUCHE (2012) the authors provided an introduction to the local floristic diversity. The Abruzzo region is an outstanding destination for botanists and orchid experts. These gems of nature occur in various parts of this region and sometimes also in small numbers. Unfortunately, the disproportionate presence of wild boars often wipes these botanical entities out for ever and, simultaneously, destroys whole populations of their parent species. We wish the institutions and

scientific community take that grim reality into account and implement measures as soon as possible to save that unique and irreplaceable botanical heritage.

Acknowledgments

The author wants to express his thanks to Francesca Romana Brunamonte, Vincenzo Catini, François Jacquet, Emanuele Gransinigh, Ugo Imprescia, Alessio Locicero, Mauro Ottonello, Giampaolo Picone, Massimo Puglisi, Giuseppe Recchia and Rolando Romolini who shared his prospections. Rolando Romolini for the proofreading of the manuscript. Thierry Pain for his assistance in English translation.

Bibliography

- CENTURIONE, N. (1999): Orchidee rare in Abruzzo.- GIROS Notizie 11: 27.
- COLELLA, A., DE SANTIS, E., FRIZZI, G. & R. SOLDATI (2011): Orchidee spontanee d'Abruzzo e chiavi analitiche digitali per il loro riconoscimento.- Lucoli (AQ).
- CONTI, F. & A. MANZI (2012): Flora vascolare della Riserva naturale regionale "Lecceta di Torino di Sangro".- Talea Ed., Atessa (CH).
- CONTI, F. & M. PELLEGRINI (1990): Orchidee spontanee d'Abruzzo.- Regione Abruzzo Assessorato all'Urbanistica e Beni Ambientali, Pescara.- COGECSTRE Edizioni, Penne (PE). 191 pp.
- CONTI, F. & D. TINTI (2008): Il Lago di Campotosto e la sua flora. Sambuceto (CH).- 160 pp.
- CONTI, F. (1995): Prodrómo della flora del Parco Nazionale d'Abruzzo.- Almadue, Roma.
- CONTI, F. (1998): Flora d'Abruzzo [reprint of: An annotated check-list of the flora of the Abruzzo].- Bocconeia 10. 273 pp.
- CONTI, F., BARTOLUCCI, F., CATONICA, C., D'ONOFRIO, G., LONDRILLO, L., MANZI, A. & D. TINTI (2006): Aggiunte alla flora d'Abruzzo II contributo.- Inform. Bot. Ital. 38(1): 113-116.
- DAISS H. & H. DAISS, (1996): Orchideen um die Majella (Abruzzen, Italien).- J. Eur. Orch. 28(4): 603-640.
- DELFORGE, P. (2003): Contribution à la connaissance des orchidées printanières de Calabre (Italie) et description d'*Ophrys brutia* sp. nova.- Naturalistes Belges, 84: 55-94.
- DI CECCO, M. & A. PEZZETTA (2012): Le *Orchidaceae* di Palena (Chieti, Abruzzo).- GIROS Notizie 50: 19-23.

- DI PEDE, A. (2001): *Ophrys sphegodes* Mill. subsp. *majellensis* H. & H. Daiss e altre *Orchidaceae* della bassa Val Roveto.- GIROS Notizie 18: 14-20.
- DI SANTO, D. & A. PEZZETTA (2012): Le *Orchidaceae* di Lama dei Peligni.- GIROS Notizie 49: 71-74.
- GALETTI, G. (1995): Fiori della Majella. D'Abruzzo.- Libri, Ed. Menabo, Ortona (CH).
- GRIEBL, N. (2010): Die Orchideen der Abruzzen.- Ber. Arbeitskrs. Heim. Orchid. 27(2): 123-170.
- HERTEL, S. & H. PRESSER (2006): Zur Kenntnis der italienischen Orchideen.- J. Eur. Orch. 38 (3): 485-532.
- HERTEL, S. & H. PRESSER (2009): Zur Kenntnis der italienischen Orchideen – Nachtrag.- J. Eur. Orch. 41(1): 195-209.
- LASTORIA, M. (1988): Orchidee in Abruzzo.- Edizioni Deltagrafica, Teramo.
- PARIS, P. & S. SCIVOLA (2011): *Ophrys speculum* Link: un'altra segnalazione per l'Abruzzo.- GIROS Notizie 48: 62-63.
- PETRUCCI, F. (2013): Gioielli della natura tra il Parco Nazionale d'Abruzzo e il Monte Vettore.- GIROS Notizie 53: 97-102.
- PEZZETTA, A. (2013): Le *Orchidaceae* d'Abruzzo.- GIROS Notizie 52: 65-76.
- ROMOLINI R. & R. SOCA (2011a): New species in the genus *Ophrys* (*Orchidaceae*) to the Italian and French Florae.- J. Eur. Orch. 43(4): 759-784.
- ROMOLINI, R. & R. SOCA (2011b): Una stazione abruzzese di *Ophrys lacaitae* Lojac., nuovo limite Nord per la specie in Italia.- GIROS Notizie 46: 48-49.
- ROMOLINI, R. & R. SOUCHE (2012): *Ophrys* d'Italia.- Éditions Sococor. 576 pp.
- SOUCHE, R. (2008a): Hybrides d'*Ophrys* du bassin méditerranéen occidental.- Éditions Sococor, Saint-Martin-de-Londres. 288 pp.
- SOUCHE, R. (2008b): Presenza di *Ophrys riojana* Hermosilla in Italia.- GIROS Notizie 38: 41-43.
- TAMMARO, F. (1986): Documenti per la conoscenza naturalistica della Majella: repertorio sistematico della flora. Centro Servizi Culturali, Chieti.
- TINTI, D. & F. CONTI (2002): *Orchidaceae* rinvenute presso il lago di Campotosto (L'Aquila, Abruzzo).- GIROS Notizie 19: 21-25.

Address of author

Romieg Soca, 7 Route des Cévennes
 F - 34380 Saint-Martin-de-Londres, France
 E-Mail: rsouche@yahoo.fr

Fig. 2: *Ophrys* ×*palenae* (*O. brutia* × *O. passionis majellensis*), Abruzzo (CH), Palena, . 26.5.2011. Fig. 3: *Ophrys* ×*recchiaie* (*O. dinarica* × *O. incubacea*), Abruzzo (AQ), Collepietro, . 20.5.2011. Fig. 4a, 4b: *Ophrys* ×*vernacchiaie* (*O. brutia* × *O. romolinii*), Abruzzo (CH), Gamberale. 26.5.2011 phot. RS (from top left to bottom right).

Fig. 5: *Ophrys* ×*brunamontei* (*O. dinarica* × *O. passionis majellensis*), Abruzzo (CH), Palena, 26.5.2011. Fig. 6: *Ophrys* ×*impresciae* (*O. dinarica* × *O. pinguis*), Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 8.6.2011. Fig. 7a, 7b: *Ophrys* ×*piconei* (*O. dinarica* × *O. romolinii*), Abruzzo (AQ), Aielli, 23.5.2011, phot. RS (from top left to bottom right).

Fig. 8: *Ophrys* ×*capistrelloi* (*O. dinarica* × *O. tetraloniae*), Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 8.6.2011., Fig. 9: *Ophrys* ×*lociceroides* (*O. lucana* × *O. passionis majellensis*), Abruzzo (CH), Palena, 6.6.2010. Fig. 10: *Ophrys* ×*catinii* (*O. pinguis* × *O. romolinii*), Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 22.5.2013. Fig. 11: *Ophrys* ×*pescocanalei* (*O. pinguis* × *O. tetraloniae*), Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 8.6.2011 phot. RS (from top left to bottom right).

Fig. 12: *Ophrys brutia*, Abruzzo (AQ), Aielli, 23.5.2011.

Fig. 13: *Ophrys passionis majellensis*. Abruzzo (CH), Palena, 10.6.2011.

Fig. 14: *Ophrys romolinii*. Abruzzo (AQ), Collepietro, 20.5.2011.

Fig. 15: *Ophrys lucana*. Basilicata (PZ), Bella, 16.5.2007.

phot. RS (from top left to bottom right).

Fig. 16: *Ophrys tetraloniae*. Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 8.6.2011.

Fig. 17: *Ophrys dinarica*. Abruzzo (AQ), Lecce nei Marsi, 29.5.2012.

Fig. 18: *Ophrys pinguis*. Abruzzo (AQ), Capistrello, 22.5.2011.
 phot. RS (from top to bottom right).